

PREDICTION OF CRACK DEVELOPMENT AND STIFFNESS DEGRADATION IN ANGLE-PLY FILAMENT WOUND PIPES

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ABSTRACT

An analytical model for the prediction of stiffness reduction in 3D angle-ply structures is presented. The model assumes a repeated and symmetrical crack pattern in the material when subjected to external loads of sufficient magnitude. A 3D displacement field involving unknown functions is assumed for a cracked element consisting of θ and $-\theta$ layers, and boundary conditions on displacements are enforced on the assumed displacement field. Using the theorem of minimum potential energy the unknown functions are determined. Both numerical analysis (finite element) and experiments were carried out to verify the validity of the model.

1. BACKGROUND

Low pressure GRP-pipes are being used in increasing extent on the offshore installations in the North sea, mostly in cooling or fire protection systems where the pressure used is usually below 25 bar. Because of good corrosion properties the GRP pipes might be good candidates for the transport of hydrocarbons. Although GRP pipes have been used as flowlines in USA for several years, no GRP pipelines have been used for transport of hydrocarbons on the Norwegian sector in the North sea. In such flowlines the pressure could be 10 times higher than the pressure in the already installed GRP-pipes [1]. From a security point of view it is essential to have methods for prediction of the condition of the pipes during operation conditions, otherwise no use of these materials in critical application will be accepted. One damage mode which is of great importance is microcracking. The appearance of microcracking in fiber reinforced composite laminates has resolved in numerous scientific studies covering this phenomena [2]. Although formation of these cracks does not lead to catastrophic failure, it causes stiffness reduction and other undesirable effects. One example is weeping in piping systems, i.e. fluid penetration in the tubewall which again alter the long term behavior of the composite (aging effects etc.) In most of these studies the transverse cracking in crossply laminates has been considered and except for a few of these studies [3] they deal only with cracks in the 90° of the crossply and almost exclusively have 2D cases been analyzed.

2. THEORETICAL MODEL

Consider a tubular shell that is built up by orthotropic θ and $-\theta$ layers. Because of the thin walled structure the laminate can be approximated with a plane laminate. Consider two connected layers k and $k+1$ as shown in fig.1:

Figure.1

The intermediate crack distance d is a function of winding angle (α) and loading. Transformation of coordinates and displacements from the ξ, η -system to the x, y system is given in eqn (1-2).

$$\frac{x}{d} = \xi \cdot \cos\alpha - \eta \cdot \sin(90 - \alpha) = (\xi - \eta) \cdot \cos\alpha \tag{1}$$

$$\frac{y}{d} = \xi \cdot \sin\alpha + \eta \cdot \cos(90 - \alpha) = (\xi + \eta) \cdot \sin\alpha$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = d \cdot \begin{bmatrix} c & -c \\ s & s \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \end{bmatrix} \therefore \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2dcs} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} s & c \\ -s & c \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} \therefore \begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c & -c \\ s & s \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} u_\xi \\ u_\eta \end{bmatrix} \tag{2}$$

2.1. Compatibility strains/displacements.

The strains in x, y -system can then be expressed in ξ, η coordinates as follows:

$$\epsilon_x = \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial \eta} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{2d} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \right) \cdot (u_\xi - u_\eta) \tag{3a}$$

$$\epsilon_y = \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial \eta} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{2d} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \right) \cdot (u_\xi + u_\eta) \tag{3b}$$

$$\gamma_{xy} = \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{2d} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{c}{s}(u_\xi - u_\eta) + \frac{s}{c}(u_\xi + u_\eta) \right) \tag{3c}$$

$$\epsilon_z = \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} = \epsilon_{oz} \tag{3d}$$

$$\gamma_{xz} = \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial \zeta} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{t} \cdot c \frac{\partial}{\partial \zeta} \cdot (u_\xi - u_\eta) \tag{3e}$$

$$\gamma_{yz} = \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial \zeta} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{t} \cdot s \frac{\partial}{\partial \zeta} \cdot (u_\xi - u_\eta) \quad (3f)$$

2.2 The displacement functions.

Displacement functions for the cracked element, referred to as the unit cell must be formulated. The displacement functions can be described by interpolation functions of varying complexity. Two models will be considered where the displacement fields are described by use of one and two unknown functions respectively.

Figure 2.

It is assumed that at $\zeta=0+$ side of the laminate the displacement field for model 1 is:

$$u_\eta^u = \frac{1}{2} \cdot ((\xi - \eta) \cdot u_\eta^1 + (\xi + \eta) \cdot u_\eta^2) \quad (4)$$

and for model 2:

$$u_\eta^u = \frac{1}{2} \cdot ((\xi - \bar{g}_1(\eta)) \cdot u_\eta^1 + (\xi + \bar{g}_1(\eta)) \cdot u_\eta^2) \quad (5)$$

i.e. the displacement transverse to the fibers. At $\zeta=0$ the two layers are perfectly connected, which means for $\zeta=0-$ the following must be satisfied:

$$u_\eta^l = u_\eta^u \quad (6)$$

Notice that u_η^1 is the displacement in the direction of the fibre. To obtain compatibility the displacement fields in η, ξ directions must interpolate equal in the $\zeta=0$ plane.

The following displacement functions exhibits the required symmetry, compatibility and takes into account the presence of a crack parallel to the fibers:

Model 1:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{\xi}(\xi, \eta) &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\xi - \eta) \cdot u_{\xi}^1 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\xi + \eta) \cdot u_{\xi}^2 \\
 u_{\eta}(\xi, \eta, \zeta) &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot ((\xi - \eta) \cdot u_{\eta}^1 + (\xi + \eta) \cdot u_{\eta}^2 + g(\eta) \cdot \phi(\zeta)) \\
 u_{\zeta} &= \varepsilon_{0z} \cdot t \cdot \zeta
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

In this approach only one unknown function is involved in the displacement field.

Model 2:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{\xi}(\xi, \eta) &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\xi - \bar{g}_1(\eta)) \cdot u_{\xi}^1 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\xi + \bar{g}_1(\eta)) \cdot u_{\xi}^2 \\
 u_{\eta}(\xi, \eta, \zeta) &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot ((\xi - \bar{g}_1(\eta)) \cdot u_{\eta}^1 + (\xi + \bar{g}_1(\eta)) \cdot u_{\eta}^2 + \bar{g}_2(\eta) \cdot \phi(\zeta)) \\
 u_{\zeta} &= \varepsilon_{0z} \cdot t \cdot \zeta
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where $\bar{g}_1 = \frac{1}{2}$

Hence two unknown functions must be determined for model 2.

2.3. The strain energy of the unit cell.

The unknown functions $g(\eta), g_1(\eta)$ and $g_2(\eta)$ are determined by utilizing the theorem of minimum potential energy. Linear elastic behavior and small deformations are assumed. The strain energy density for an elastic material given by [4] :

$$W = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sigma_{ij} \cdot \varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot C_{ijkl} \cdot \varepsilon_{ij} \tag{9}$$

where C_{ijkl} are the transformed stiffnesses for the composite layers. The potential energy for the whole element is then given by:

$$U = \frac{2t}{2d^2 sc} \int_0^1 \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 W \cdot d\xi \cdot d\eta \cdot d\zeta \tag{10}$$

Since the variation of U i.e. δU must be zero for an arbitrary virtual displacement one need to consider only eqn. (11) :

$$U = \int_0^1 \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 W \cdot d\xi \cdot d\eta \cdot d\zeta = \int_0^1 \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 C_{ijkl} \cdot \varepsilon_{ij} d\xi \cdot d\eta \cdot d\zeta \tag{11}$$

The displacement field is now given a small variation . Among all admissible displacement variations δu_i (i.e. all variations that satisfies all symmetry and boundary conditions and are continuous over the element and its boundaries), the desired displacement field is distinguished by [5]:

$$\delta U = 0 \tag{12}$$

The expression of the potential energy for the cracked element can be expressed by the unknown functions and their respective variations. The variation in the potential energy

due to an arbitrary, but admissible variation of the displacement field can be written as eqn. (13) and eqn.(14) for the two models respectively:

Model 1:

$$\delta U = \int_0^1 \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 (C_{11} \cdot (\alpha \cdot \alpha_x \cdot \phi \cdot \delta g' + \alpha^2 \cdot g' \cdot \delta g' \cdot \phi^2) + \dots + (C_{45} \cdot \delta_x \cdot \delta_y \cdot \phi'^2 \cdot g \cdot \delta g) + \dots + (C_{66} \cdot (\beta \cdot \beta_x \cdot \phi \cdot \delta g' + \beta^2 \cdot g' \cdot \delta g' \cdot \phi^2) d\eta \cdot d\xi \cdot d\zeta \quad (13)$$

where $\alpha_x.. \delta_{zx}$ are constants dependent on the corner displacements, crack density and winding angle.

Model 2:

$$\delta U = \int_0^1 \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 (\alpha_1 \cdot (\delta \bar{g}'_1(\xi) + \delta \bar{g}'_1(\eta)) + \alpha_{12} \cdot (\delta \bar{g}'_2(\eta) \cdot \delta \bar{g}'_2(\eta) + \delta \bar{g}'_2(\xi) \cdot \delta \bar{g}'_2(\xi)) \cdot \phi^2 + \dots + \beta_2 \cdot \epsilon_{0z} \cdot \delta \epsilon_{0z} + \beta_8 \cdot \phi \cdot \delta \epsilon_{0z} \cdot (\delta \bar{g}'_2(\eta) \cdot \delta \bar{g}'_2(\eta)) + \gamma_1 \cdot (\delta \bar{g}'_2(\eta) \cdot \delta \bar{g}'_2(\eta) + \delta \bar{g}'_2(\eta) \cdot \delta \bar{g}'_2(\eta)) \cdot \phi^2) \cdot d\eta \cdot d\xi \cdot d\zeta \quad (14)$$

where $\alpha_1'.. \gamma_1$ are constants dependent on the corner displacements, crack density, winding angle and C_{ijkl} .

As stated earlier the variation of U must be zero for all combinations of $\delta g(\eta)$, $\delta g_1(\eta)$, $\delta g_2(\eta)$ and $\delta \epsilon_{0z}$ for the two models. Hence from eqn.(13) we obtain the following system of equations for model 1:

$$\begin{aligned} -g'' + \alpha_7 \cdot g &= 0 \\ \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 \cdot \epsilon_{0z} - 2 \cdot g'(1) &= 0 \\ \alpha_4 + \alpha_5 \cdot \epsilon_{0z} + \alpha_6 \cdot g(1) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where $\alpha_1.. \alpha_7..$ are dependent on $(\alpha_x.. \delta_{zx} , C_{11}..C_{66}, \phi(\zeta))$.

For model 2, eqn.(14) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} g_1'' &= \alpha_{20} \cdot g_2'' \\ g_2 + \alpha_{21} \cdot g_1'' + \alpha_{22} \cdot g_2'' &= 0 \\ g_1(1) &= 1/2 \\ \alpha_{32} + \alpha_{33} \cdot g_1'(1) + g_2'(1) + \alpha_{34} \cdot \epsilon_{0z} &= 0 \\ \alpha_{30} + g_2'(1) + \alpha_{31} \cdot \epsilon_{0z} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $\alpha_{20}.. \alpha_{34}..$ are dependent on $(\alpha_1'.. \gamma_1, \phi(\zeta))$.

By solving the differential equation and using the natural boundary conditions for the two models, the unknown constants in the expressions for the displacements are obtained.

3. STIFFNESS REDUCTION AND CRITICAL PRESSURE VS. DAMAGE.

By actually observing the crack pattern in an $\pm\theta$ wound pipe subjected to pure axial load or internal pressure one can find that for both short term and long term tests the pattern will consist of characteristic areas defined by winding angle and loading mode. To simulate multiple cracking the length of the element in both $\eta \xi$ directions is divided by a factor

two. The motivation for doing so is that experiments show that the cracks are distributed approximately uniform in the cracking layers, and that the size of the characteristic areas are reduced by a factor four but not the shape going from one damage state to another. The total force axial and hoop directions, N_x, N_y respectively are:

$$N_x = \sigma_x \cdot t \cdot 2 \cdot d_y \quad \therefore \quad N_y = \sigma_y \cdot t \cdot 2 \cdot d_x \quad (17)$$

These forces can be described by linear equations of the displacements in axial and hoop direction as follows:

$$N_x = \omega_1 \cdot u_{y2} + \omega_2 \cdot u_{x1} \quad \therefore \quad N_y = \mu_1 \cdot u_{y2} + \mu_2 \cdot u_{x1} \quad (18)$$

By considering the following two cases one can calculate the influence numbers in eqn.(18) i.e. $\omega_1, \omega_2, \mu_1, \mu_2$:

$$\begin{aligned} 1. \quad u_{x1} = 0 \quad , \quad u_{y2} = 1 &\Rightarrow \omega_1 = N_x^I \quad , \quad \mu_1 = N_y^I \\ 2. \quad u_{x1} = 1 \quad , \quad u_{y2} = 0 &\Rightarrow \omega_2 = N_x^{II} \quad , \quad \mu_2 = N_y^{II} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Combining eqn.(18-19) and Hookes law for the laminate the gross axial and hoop elastic moduli as a function of the unit cell size can be expressed as:

$$E_x = \frac{(\omega_1 \cdot \mu_2 - \omega_2^2) \cdot d_x}{t \cdot d_y \cdot \mu_2} \quad \therefore \quad E_y = \frac{(\omega_1 \cdot \mu_2 - \omega_2^2) \cdot d_y}{t \cdot d_x \cdot \omega_1} \quad (20)$$

The stiffness degradation of the moduli in each direction has been made dimensionless by dividing with the moduli for the uncracked laminate(i.e. when $d \rightarrow \infty$).

By using the results for the stiffness degradation the critical pressure for each crack density can be calculated. Cracking occurs when ϵ_η at point P in fig. 1 reaches the critical transverse strain ϵ_{crit} for the material.

$$P_{crit} = \frac{\epsilon_{crit} \cdot h \cdot (\alpha_1 \cdot \beta_2 - \alpha_2 \cdot \beta_1)}{r \cdot t \cdot (\delta_1 \cdot (2 \cdot d_y \cdot \beta_2 - d_x \cdot \alpha_2) + \delta_2 \cdot (d_x \cdot \alpha_1 - 2 \cdot d_y \cdot \beta_1))} \quad (21)$$

where h is the tubewall thickness and the transverse strain ϵ_η can be expressed as:

$$\epsilon_\eta = \delta_1 \cdot u_{x1} + \delta_2 \cdot u_{y2} \quad (22)$$

4. NUMERICAL SOLUTION .

The 3D problem was modeled by the use of the finite element code ANSYS [6]. The model was built up by two orthotropic layers at respectively θ and $-\theta$ orientations of the reinforcements, and for each layer two traction free surfaces exists, i.e crack surfaces. A coarse model is shown in fig.7, to indicate the elementmodel build-up.. The element type was solid95, a 20-nodes structural element.

5. EXPERIMENTS.

Experiments were carried out on $\pm 55^\circ$ angle ply 100mm glassfiber/epoxy pipe produced by Wavin Repox (Holland), subjected to internal pressure up to 250 bars. Stress vs. strain curves were obtained for the different pressure levels and the damage evolution in the

material (transverse matrix cracking) were followed by transmission light based visual inspection and by acoustic emission monitoring. Tests were also performed on small 18mm $\pm 45^\circ$ glassfiber/epoxy pipes produced by Courtaulds Advanced Materials (France) in torsion to obtain uniform crack distribution and compression to measure the stiffness decrease as a function of crack density.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main aim of this study was to obtain an analytical model that predicts the stiffness degradation and critical pressure due to intraply cracks in a $\pm \theta^\circ$ angle ply pipe structure. The results in fig. 3 and 4 shows that the proposed models give good prediction as compared to the numerical model of the stiffness degradation of angle ply composite pipes, both for the $\pm 45^\circ$ and $\pm 55^\circ$ tube. Good correlation was also between theoretical, numerical and experimental results. Rather complex boundary conditions are assumed for the finite element model. Load transferring planes are considered to remain plane during deformation of the model. It is also assumed for both the numerical and analytical models that the influence of the global boundaries can be neglected, because the unit cell is assumed to be situated in the middle of the tube wall. For the $\pm 55^\circ$ pipe the experimentally obtained crack pattern was to inhomogenous to draw any firm conclusion regarding the stiffness degradation as a function of crack density. The stiffness however was measured after loading up to different pressure levels, and these values were compared to the predicted stiffness loss deduced from the critical pressure vs. crack density relation (see fig.5,6).

For the $\pm 45^\circ$ pipe the crack density was easily measured by visual inspection, and the crack pattern were distributed uniformly in the tubewall. The test results for the $\pm T$ (torsion-torsion) were compared to the work of B. Maquire et.al [7], and these results were compared to the stiffness degradation given by the models.

FIGURES.

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Table 1: Transverse isotropic engineering constants.

Properties:	Mat. 1	Mat. 2
Ex	42.4 GPa	39.6 GPa
Ey	13.1 GPa	9.7 GPa
Gxy	4.7 GPa	5.1 GPa
vxy	0.26	0.28
vyz	0.22	0.26
t _{ply}	0.20 mm	0.28 mm

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